

Identifying and evaluating key excipients in commercial oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations: A descriptive study of formulation approaches and selected safety concerns

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Abstract

Excipients are inactive substances required for the preparation of pharmaceutical forms. The efficacy, safety, and quality of syrup formulations depend on their composition, including excipients. Oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations are most commonly used for pediatric and geriatric populations. Forty-one oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations were initially identified. Of these, 30 formulations with complete excipient information in their patient information leaflets (PILs) were included in the final analysis, while 11 formulations were excluded due to incomplete excipient data. The frequency of each excipient class was determined. The associations between the sweeteners or preservatives used in the analyzed oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations and H₁ antihistamine classes were observed. These associations are exploratory in nature and do not reflect causal relationships; they should be interpreted with caution because of the small sample size and lack of homogeneity. This assessment is based solely on the available descriptive information, without data on the concentrations of the excipients. In the analyzed oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, propylene glycol, sorbitol, sodium benzoate, strawberry flavor, Sunset Yellow FCF, and citric acid/sodium citrate were the most commonly used co-solvent, sweetener, preservative, flavoring agent, colorant, and buffering agent, respectively. The results of this study illustrate the patterns of excipient use only within the formulations that were analyzed.

Keywords

excipients, pediatric formulations, safety concerns, syrup

Introduction

Excipients are inactive substances used alongside the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) in the preparation of pharmaceutical dosage forms. They do not possess pharmacological or therapeutic activity and are primarily included to support formulation performance (Ways 2025). A range of excipients is used to facilitate manufacturing, maintain stability, enhance bioavailability, and improve patient acceptance through taste and texture (Gaikwad et al.

2024; Kosenko et al. 2025; Wasiullah et al. 2025). One of the most important considerations before using excipients in oral syrup formulations is their safety profile. This is especially important for pediatric patients because physiological differences and increased sensitivity may lead to allergic reactions or serious side effects in some cases, even at low concentrations (Balbani et al. 2006; Abrantes et al. 2016; European Medicines Agency 2018; Bobillot et al. 2024). The selection and use of excipients in oral formulations

are not only based on their functional roles but are also guided by regulatory frameworks that emphasize safety evaluation, dose-dependent effects, and appropriate use in specific patient populations (Rowe et al. 2000; Dohrn et al. 2021). Therefore, pharmaceutical manufacturers must provide clear information about excipients, including their names, functional categories, and any adverse effects.

Oral pharmaceutical dosage forms, including syrups, are essential for drug delivery. They are the most popular because of their ease of administration and better patient compliance, especially among pediatric and geriatric populations, as well as patients who have difficulty swallowing tablets and capsules or individuals who require precise, weight-based dosing (Fox 2014; Aulton and Taylor 2022).

H₁ antihistamines are mainstay treatments for allergic conditions such as allergic rhinitis and urticaria (Linton et al. 2023). They are classified into first-generation (sedating) and second-generation (non-sedating) agents. First-generation antihistamines include ketotifen, chlorpheniramine, dimetindene, and triprolidine, whereas second-generation agents include loratadine, desloratadine, cetirizine, and levocetirizine. First-generation H₁ antagonists are highly lipophilic, enabling them to easily cross the blood-brain barrier. These two classes differ in their pharmacological properties and safety profiles, with first-generation antihistamines generally associated with central nervous system (CNS) effects, while second-generation agents are considered to have a more favorable safety profile, with reduced sedative potential (Parisi et al. 2020; Linton et al. 2023).

The literature indicates that limited data are available on the type, frequency, and commonality of excipients in H₁ antihistamine syrups. Based on available published studies, the frequency and prevalence of excipient use in commercially available oral H₁ antihistamine syrups marketed in Iraq have not been adequately reported. This may be due to the absence of excipient-labeling regulations and inconsistent disclosure practices in Iraq. These factors represent key aspects that should be taken into consideration. The identification of excipient types is essential for accurate evaluation and for selecting appropriate products for specific patient populations, especially pediatric and geriatric populations. A complete identification of the commonly used excipients is important to provide insight into industry-standard choices. This may provide descriptive insight into formulation practices, regional regulations, and consumer preferences and may also reduce the time and cost associated with developing new products.

Aims of this study

1. Determine the frequency of the main excipients in oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations.
2. Provide a functional description of each excipient.
3. Analyze the relationship between each excipient type and H₁ antihistamine class, if applicable.
4. Discuss the safety of the most commonly used excipients.

Materials and methods

Selection of formulations

This study was designed as a descriptive survey of locally available oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations. The inclusion criteria for H₁ antihistamine oral syrup formulations were the availability of patient information leaflets (PILs). Accordingly, 41 formulations were initially identified; however, only 30 formulations with complete excipient information in their PILs were included in the final analysis, while 11 formulations were excluded due to incomplete excipient data. The selected oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations cover first – and second-generation H₁ antihistamines. These formulations included eight H₁ antihistamine APIs: four first-generation antihistamines (chlorpheniramine, ketotifen, dimetindene, and triprolidine) and four second-generation antihistamines (desloratadine, loratadine, cetirizine, and levocetirizine). The formulations were collected by visiting a number of different community pharmacies in Iraq, where H₁ antihistamine formulations available during the data collection period were identified. In addition to different H₁ antihistamine formulations, different brands of the same API were selected as distinct formulations. The formulations were manufactured in a range of countries, including Iraq, Egypt, Syria, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, the U.A.E., Oman, Turkey, India, Germany, France, and Ireland. Although the oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations were not restricted to those exclusively marketed as pediatric formulations, in general, oral syrups are predominantly prescribed for pediatric patients. Most of the included formulations provided explicit pediatric dosing instructions in their package leaflets. This supports the focus on safety considerations in pediatric patients in the analysis and discussion. The frequency of excipients—solvents, co-solvents, sweeteners, antimicrobial preservatives, flavoring agents, colorants, buffering agents, and chelating agents—in different oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations was analyzed based on the data contained in PILs. The PILs were systematically reviewed to identify all listed excipients for each formulation. Then, the extracted excipients were categorized according to their functional roles in pharmaceutical formulations. The analysis was limited to excipients explicitly listed in the formulation leaflets, and only formulations with complete excipient data were included. Data were collected and analyzed from September to December 2025. No chemical or quantitative analysis was performed, and the study relied solely on data contained in drug PILs. The results of this study are limited to the formulations analyzed in this sample and do not necessarily represent all formulations available on the market.

Categorization of excipients for analysis

Based on the excipient monographs from the “*Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients*,” the function of the excipients in the oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations was determined (Sheskey et al. 2017). Sometimes, manufacturers provided information on the function of the excipients in the patient information leaflet (PIL), which was also

included in the analysis. All excipients used as solvents, co-solvents, sweeteners, antimicrobial preservatives, flavoring agents, colorants, buffering agents, and chelating agents were identified. Their occurrence and frequency (as a percentage) in the formulations were then calculated.

Statistical analysis

Fisher's exact test was used to evaluate the association between the type of sweetener or preservative and the H₁ antihistamine classes in the oral syrups. Fisher's exact test was chosen because it is an appropriate method for analyzing categorical data with small sample sizes or sparse distributions. A *p*-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 25.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was not required for this study because it was based solely on publicly available data from formulation information leaflets and did not involve human participants.

Results

The APIs of the formulations used in this study were ketotifen, chlorpheniramine, dimetindene, triprolidine, desloratadine, loratadine, cetirizine, and levocetirizine. Of the 41 identified formulations, 18 were classified as first-generation H₁ antihistamines and 23 were classified as second-generation H₁ antihistamines. Eleven of the identified formulations were excluded due to incomplete excipient information in their PILs. Only 30 formulations were analyzed (Table 1). Desloratadine was the most common API among the analyzed oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, whereas cetirizine, levocetirizine, and triprolidine were the least frequently used (3.33%).

For all 30 analyzed oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, water was used as a solvent. Four co-solvents

were used in these analyzed formulations. Propylene glycol was the most common co-solvent, followed by glycerin, ethanol, and triacetin (Table 2). These co-solvents were used either alone or in combination with another co-solvent. Glycerin was most commonly used with propylene glycol, and Fig. 1 illustrates the pattern of co-solvent combinations across the analyzed formulations. Three of the analyzed oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations did not use any co-solvent, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Types of co-solvents and sweeteners, their frequency, and percentage in the analyzed formulations. Percentages are calculated based on the number of formulations that listed the excipients (*N* = 30).

Co-solvent	Frequency in formulations <i>n</i> (%)	Sweeteners	Frequency in formulations <i>n</i> (%)
Propylene glycol	20 (66.67)	Sorbitol	17 (56.67)
Glycerin (Glycerol)	11 (36.67)	Sucrose	18 (60)
Ethanol	4 (13.33)	Saccharin sodium	8 (19.35)
Triacetin	1 (3.33)	Maltitol	3 (10)
No co-solvent	3 (10)	Sucralose	1 (3.33)
		Lycasin	2 (6.67)
		Sodium cyclamate	1 (3.33)
		No sweetener	3 (10)

Seven different sweeteners were identified among the analyzed formulations. Sucrose was the most commonly used sweetener, followed by sorbitol, which was often used in combination with sucrose. Less frequently used sweeteners were sucralose and sodium cyclamate (Table 2). Fig. 2 illustrates patterns of sweetener use across the analyzed formulations. Among these formulations, 10 used a single sweetener, while others used combinations, and three did not contain any sweetener. An exploratory statistically significant association was observed between H₁ antihistamine class and the type of sweetener used (Fisher's exact test, *p* < 0.001), which should be interpreted with caution because of the small sample size and heterogeneity of the analyzed formulations. Certain sweetener combinations, such as sorbitol and sucrose, were observed in 60% of desloratadine formulations, while sucrose alone or in combination was observed in 87.5% of loratadine formulations.

Table 1. Active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), API class, pharmaceutical formulation type, frequency, and percentage of analyzed formulations (*N* = 30).

API	API Class	Pharmaceutical formulation type	Frequency of formulations <i>n</i> (%)
Desloratadine	Second-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	10 (33.33)
Loratadine	Second-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	8 (26.67)
Cetirizine	Second-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	1 (3.33)
Levocetirizine	Second-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	1 (3.33)
Ketotifen	First-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	2 (6.67)
Chlorpheniramine	First-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	5 (16.67)
Dimetindene	First-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	2 (6.67)
Triprolidine	First-generation H ₁ antagonists	Syrup	1 (3.33)
Total			30 (100)

Note: Frequency values are presented as *n* (%); values in parentheses indicate percentages (*N* = 30).

Figure 1. Frequency of co-solvents used in the oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, applied either individually or in combination. Each formulation is named F1 to F30 to represent the 30 individual analyzed formulations (*N* = 30).

Figure 2. Frequency of sweeteners used in the oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, applied either individually or in combination. Each formulation is named F1 to F30 to represent the 30 individual analyzed formulations ($N = 30$).

Among the analyzed formulations, four different antimicrobial preservatives were identified (Table 3). All analyzed formulations contained an antimicrobial preservative. Fig. 3 illustrates patterns of preservative use across the analyzed formulations. Twenty formulations contained a single preservative, while 10 used combinations such as methyl and propyl parabens. An exploratory statistically significant association was also identified between H₁ antihistamine class and preservative type (Fisher's exact test, $p < 0.001$) and should be interpreted with caution because

Table 3. Types of antimicrobial preservatives, flavoring agents, and colorants; their frequency; and percentage in the analyzed formulations. Percentages are calculated based on the number of formulations that listed the excipients ($N = 30$).

Antimicrobial preservatives	Frequency in formulations n (%)	Flavoring agents	Frequency in formulations n (%)	Colorants	Frequency in formulations n (%)
Sodium benzoate	19 (63.33)	Strawberry flavor	5 (16.67)	Sunset Yellow FCF	5 (16.67)
Benzyl alcohol	1 (3.33)	Orange flavor	3 (10)	Tartrazine (FD&C Yellow No. 5, E102)	1 (3.33)
Methyl paraben	11 (36.67)	Bubble gum flavor	1 (3.33)	Quinoline Yellow (E104)	1 (3.33)
Propyl paraben	9 (30)	Tutti-frutti flavor	4 (13.33)	Ponceau 4R (E124)	1 (3.33)
		Banana flavor	4 (13.33)	Carmoisine (E122)	2 (6.67)
		Vanillin flavor	2 (6.67)	No colorants	20 (66.67)
		Pineapple Flavor	1 (3.33)		
		Peach flavor	2 (6.67)		
		Raspberry flavor	1 (3.33)		
		Mix Fruit flavor	1 (3.33)		
		Flavor/flavored syrup base	2 (6.67)		
		No flavoring agents	6 (20)		

Note: Frequency values are presented as n (%); values in parentheses indicate percentages.

*FD&C = Food, Drug, and Cosmetic; used in the United States to indicate that a colorant is certified for use in foods, drugs, and cosmetics by the U.S. FDA.

**Sunset Yellow FCF includes FD&C Yellow No. 6, Spectracol FD&C Yellow No. 6, Sunset Yellow, and FD&C Yellow No. 6 dye, as they have the same chemical structure (FD&C Yellow No. 6 → U.S. FDA name, Sunset Yellow FCF → international / EU name, E110 → the EU food additive code, Spectracol → brand name only, not a new excipient, and "dye" → descriptive, not regulatory).

Figure 3. Frequency of antimicrobial preservatives used in the oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, applied either individually or in combination. Each formulation is named F1 to F30 to represent the 30 individual analyzed formulations ($N = 30$).

of the small sample size and heterogeneity of the analyzed formulations. This was reflected in the more frequent observation of sodium benzoate in second-generation H₁ antihistamine formulations, whereas methyl and propyl parabens were more frequently associated with first-generation antihistamine formulations.

Eleven different flavoring agents were identified among the analyzed formulations (Table 3). Strawberry flavor was the most common, followed by tutti-frutti and banana flavors. Fruit-based flavors such as orange, bubble gum, vanillin, pineapple, peach, raspberry, and mixed fruit flavors were frequently used. All analyzed formulations containing flavoring agents included a single flavoring agent, except for two formulations that contained two. Six analyzed formulations did not contain any flavoring agent despite the known bitterness of the APIs. Additionally, two analyzed formulations contained unspecified flavoring agents and were labeled only as "flavor" or "flavored syrup base" (Table 3).

Five synthetic colorants were identified in 33.33% of the analyzed formulations. Sunset Yellow FCF was the most frequently used colorant among formulations containing colorants. Most formulations (66.67%) did not contain colorants (Table 3).

Regarding buffering agents, four different buffering systems were identified in 50% of the analyzed formulations (Table 4). The remaining formulations (50%) did not contain buffering agents. However, 33.33% included citric acid or sodium hydroxide as pH modifiers, either alone or in combination. In contrast, 16.67% contained neither buffering agents nor pH modifiers (Table 4). Fig. 4

Figure 4. Frequency of buffering agents and pH modifiers used in the oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, applied either individually or in combination. Each formulation is named F1 to F30 to represent the 30 individual analyzed formulations ($N = 30$).

Table 4. Types of buffers and pH modifiers, their frequency, and percentage in the analyzed formulations. Percentages are calculated based on the number of formulations that listed the excipients ($N = 30$).

Buffering agent	Frequency in formulations n (%)	pH modifier	Frequency in formulations n (%)***
*Citric acid/sodium citrate	12 (40)	**Citric acid	10 (33.33)
Citric acid/disodium hydrogen phosphate	1 (3.33)	Sodium hydroxide	2 (6.67)
Glacial acetic acid/sodium acetate	1 (3.33)	No pH modifier	20 (66.67%)
Phosphoric acid/sodium phosphate	1 (3.33)		
No buffering agent	15 (50)		

Note: *Citric acid/sodium citrate buffer is mentioned as citric acid anhydrous/trisodium citrate dehydrate (3), citric acid anhydrous/sodium citrate anhydrous (1), citric acid monohydrate/trisodium citrate dehydrate (3), citric acid monohydrate/sodium citrate (3), citric acid/trisodium citrate (1), and citric acid/sodium citrate (1).

** Citric acid as a pH modifier is mentioned as citric acid alone (3), citric acid anhydrous (1), and citric acid monohydrate (5).

***Frequency values are presented as n (%); values in parentheses indicate percentages. Percentages may exceed 100% because some analyzed formulations contained more than one pH modifier.

illustrates the distribution of buffering systems and pH modifiers across the analyzed formulations.

Disodium EDTA was used as a chelating agent in 50% of the analyzed formulations, while the remaining 50% did not contain any chelating agent.

Discussion

The present study examined patterns of excipient use and their characterization in oral H_1 antihistamine syrup formulations. Safety considerations were discussed from the perspective of pediatric caution, given that oral syrup formulations are frequently used in this age group. This discussion was limited to the information available in the PILs of the analyzed formulations. All safety observations remain descriptive because of the lack of data on excipient concentrations. In this context, regulatory aspects focus on excipient disclosure, clarity of information in package inserts, and caution in pediatric use, as emphasized by both the EMA and the FDA. In the present study, among the 41 identified formulations, 26.83% lacked excipient disclosure in their PILs. Inconsistent or incomplete labeling of excipients may limit the ability to assess the safety and quality of the analyzed formulations. Since some adverse effects may be related to excipients rather than the API itself, disclosure remains an important factor (Kinsella et al. 2024). A similar observation was reported in a study conducted in Hong Kong, where 63.5% of formulations lacked complete excipient information. This may indicate that this issue occurs in different regions, although it does not necessarily reflect the situation in all markets (Kan et al. 2023).

In the present study, water, the most commonly used solvent in pediatric formulations, was used in all the analyzed formulations. As most H_1 antihistamine APIs are poorly water-soluble, co-solvents are usually used to improve solubility (Bobillot et al. 2024).

The analyzed formulations showed a variety of co-solvents used, either individually or in combination. Propylene glycol was the most frequently used co-solvent in the analyzed formulations. It is characterized by its multifunctional role as a co-solvent and humectant and may also contribute to preservative effectiveness. Glycerin was also commonly used, often paired with another co-solvent. Glycerin is a multipurpose agent, as it can act as a co-solvent, sweetener, preservative, and thickening agent. The use of ethanol was limited to a small number of the analyzed formulations. It may be associated with adverse effects in pediatric populations (Rouaz et al. 2021). The least frequently used co-solvent was triacetin, despite the information in the literature regarding its safety profile and functional properties, including the improvement of syrup palatability. These findings align with the study by Kosenko et al., which also reported that propylene glycol, glycerin, and ethanol are the most commonly used co-solvents in syrup formulations, but in different percentages of 20.75%, 25.94%, and 24.53%, respectively (Kosenko et al. 2025). Bobillot et al. also reported the use of propylene glycol, glycerin, and ethanol at percentages of 15.5%, 18%, and 13%, respectively (Bobillot et al. 2024). The absence of co-solvents in some analyzed formulations may be due to formulation factors that cannot be determined from the PILs alone. The results showed the predominant use of propylene glycol in most desloratadine formulations and also in combination with glycerin in loratadine formulations. However, this finding should be interpreted with caution, given the small sample size and its heterogeneity.

However, the literature suggests that these co-solvents may be associated with adverse effects at high exposure levels in pediatric populations. Propylene glycol has been associated with CNS effects in pediatric patients (Rouaz et al. 2021). Multiple side effects of ethanol have been reported, including effects on the CNS, metabolism, and cardiovascular system when used in syrup formulations. This has been highlighted in regulatory guidance, particularly for use in young children (Clouser and Diserod 2022; Bobillot et al. 2024). Glycerin and triacetin are generally regarded as safe in the literature; however, glycerin has been associated with gastrointestinal (GI) effects (Sheskey et al. 2017). This highlights the importance of excipient disclosure and consideration in pediatric syrup formulations.

In the present study, sweeteners were present in most of the analyzed formulations, including both natural (sorbitol, sucrose, maltitol, and Lycasin®) and synthetic (saccharin sodium, sucralose, and sodium cyclamate) sweeteners. The results showed that sorbitol and sucrose were among the most commonly used sweeteners in the analyzed formulations. They have a dual role in syrup formulations, including enhancing taste and viscosity, which aids in the stability of the syrup formulations. Many of the analyzed formulations used two or three combined sweeteners. Despite the bitter taste of APIs, it was noted that a limited number of the analyzed formulations did not contain any sweetener and may have acquired the sweet taste from other excipients present in the formulation. Other studies reported the use of the same sweeteners in oral pediatric

syrup formulations, but with different proportions. Bobillot et al. reported that the most commonly used sweetener was sodium saccharin (36.5%), followed by saccharose (27%), sorbitol (14%), and aspartame (13.5%) (Bobillot et al. 2024). Kosenko et al. reported that the most commonly used sweetener was sucrose (66.51%), followed by sorbitol (29.25%) and sodium saccharin (10.85%) (Kosenko et al. 2025). An association was observed between the type of sweetener and the H₁ antihistamine class in the analyzed formulations. However, this association should be interpreted with caution because of the small sample size and heterogeneity of the sample. These variations may also be related to manufacturer-specific formulation strategies rather than formulation requirements of the API. The literature indicates considerations related to sweeteners in sensitive populations at high levels of exposure. These considerations include potential effects on the digestive system or metabolic processes. Although many of these sweeteners are approved within regulatory frameworks, their varying properties may necessitate additional consideration when used in pharmaceutical formulations (Thabuis et al. 2010; Sheskey et al. 2017; Rouaz et al. 2021; Ways 2025; Roquette 2026). However, further evaluation may be required for sodium cyclamate regarding its safety and regulatory acceptance, as it is not listed in the FDA Inactive Ingredients Database. Nevertheless, it is permitted for use as a food additive in Europe (Sheskey et al. 2017; Ways 2025).

Antimicrobial preservatives are used to prevent the growth of microorganisms and maintain the stability of the product, particularly in multi-dose formulations (Rouaz et al. 2021). The findings showed that sodium benzoate was the most commonly used preservative in the analyzed formulations. It is characterized by its broad spectrum of activity. This was followed by parabens, as methyl paraben and propyl paraben were also widely used in the analyzed formulations. These materials demonstrate effectiveness across a wide pH range. They are often used together to enhance antimicrobial efficacy (Rouaz et al. 2021; Bobillot et al. 2024). In the present study, they were observed to be used together in a number of the formulations. These findings are consistent with the study by Ways, which also reported that sodium benzoate was the most commonly used preservative in pediatric oral formulations at 38.7%, while methyl paraben and propyl paraben were found at 25.8% and 19.3%, respectively (Ways 2025). These results also align with the studies by Bobillot et al. and Kosenko et al., which indicated that methyl paraben, propyl paraben, and sodium benzoate are commonly used preservatives in pediatric oral formulations (Bobillot et al. 2024; Kosenko et al. 2025). The least frequently used preservative was benzyl alcohol, despite its antibacterial properties. In this study, some of the analyzed formulations used a single preservative, while others used a combination of more than one preservative. Using a single preservative may be associated with simpler strategies, while using a combination of preservatives is associated with broader coverage of antimicrobial activity (Ways 2025). The results showed that 85% of the second-generation H₁ antihistamine formulations contained sodium benzoate,

while 70% of the first-generation H₁ antihistamine formulations contained a combination of methyl paraben and propyl paraben. This association between preservative type and H₁ antihistamine class was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$); it should be interpreted with caution because of the small sample size and heterogeneity. Other factors such as product pH and sugar content may influence preservative selection more than the antihistamine class itself. However, this association may require further investigation through future studies with larger datasets and stratified analyses.

The preservatives identified in the present study raise considerations related to their use in pediatric formulations. Sodium benzoate has been associated with bilirubin displacement from albumin in neonates, especially given their limited metabolic capacity (European Medicines Agency 2017). Although parabens, whether methyl paraben or propyl paraben, are widely used, they have defined acceptable daily intake levels, as they have been linked to endocrine disruption in animal studies (European Medicines Agency 2015). Although these effects have not been confirmed in humans, they may warrant consideration in pediatric populations (European Medicines Agency 2015; Ways 2025). Benzyl alcohol, though effective, was less frequently used. It has been described in relation to limited metabolic capacity in neonates, with considerations reported at higher exposure levels (Rouaz et al. 2021). In this context, regulatory frameworks highlight specific considerations regarding its use in pediatric populations (European Medicines Agency 2017; Ways 2025). This reflects its rare presence in the analyzed formulations. Variations in their properties and usage requirements may necessitate additional consideration when including them in formulations intended for pediatric populations.

Flavoring agents were used in the analyzed formulations to mask or modify the bitter taste of the APIs. Fruity flavors, particularly strawberry, banana, and tutti-frutti, were commonly observed in the analyzed formulations. The study shows that 6.67% of the analyzed formulations used two types of flavoring agents, such as orange and bubble gum flavors or strawberry and banana flavors. The absence of a flavoring agent was observed in six formulations. This may be related to other excipients present in the analyzed formulations (Ways 2025). The presence of unspecified flavoring agents in some analyzed formulations may limit the clarity of information regarding excipients and add uncertainty when evaluating their use in sensitive populations. This may highlight the need for clear excipient disclosure. Some flavoring agents may raise concerns regarding allergenicity or tolerability in pediatric populations. In this context, excipient safety and disclosure remain important considerations.

In this study, five synthetic colorants were identified in a limited number of analyzed formulations. Sunset Yellow FCF was the most frequently used colorant among formulations containing colorants. In contrast, most formulations did not contain colorants, which is consistent with their limited use. These considerations remain in light of limited safety data, including data on synthetic colorants, especially

in pediatric formulations (Malkawi et al. 2022). These findings align with the study by Kosenko et al. (2025), which also reported Sunset Yellow FCF as a common colorant used in syrup formulations (7.54%) (Kosenko et al. 2025). Most of the identified colorants are approved. However, Ponceau 4R and Quinoline Yellow are not approved by the FDA, although they are permitted for use in the European Union. Although approved colorants are generally considered safe, considerations remain because of limited safety data and reported adverse effects, particularly in pediatric populations (Pérez-Ibarbia et al. 2016; Sheskey et al. 2017). Synthetic colorants have been associated with allergic reactions, but each of them may have other effects in pediatric populations. Sunset Yellow FCF has been associated with behavioral observations; Tartrazine has been linked to hypersensitivity reactions, while Carmoisine has been associated with respiratory-related observations (Pérez-Ibarbia et al. 2016; Panachiyil et al. 2019; Visternicu et al. 2025). Quinoline Yellow and Ponceau 4R have been described in relation to broader systemic effects in experimental studies (U.S. Food and Drug Administration 2023; Amchova et al. 2024).

Buffering agents or pH modifiers were observed in most of the analyzed formulations. The citric acid/sodium citrate buffer system was the most frequently used in the analyzed formulations. This system maintains an acidic environment, improves palatability, and enhances the effectiveness of preservatives. These results align with the study by Eccles, which also reported that the acetic acid/sodium acetate buffer was used in 81.67% of the formulations (Eccles 2020). Their safety considerations are mainly related to cumulative sodium exposure rather than intrinsic excipient toxicity and acidic pH-associated GI effects, which may be of greater relevance in pediatric and elderly patients. The absence of buffering agents was observed in some of the analyzed formulations, particularly in cases where the drug is in the form of a soluble salt or may be stabilized by other means. This may be related to reducing the amount of excipients and sodium exposure, which is generally preferred in formulations intended for pediatric patients. Citric acid was identified in some of the analyzed formulations as a pH modifier, either alone or in combination with sodium hydroxide. It was also used to mask the bitter taste of APIs. In addition, it functions as an antioxidant, a chelating agent, and a preservative. Its use is approved by both the EMA and the FDA (Sheskey et al. 2017). It is generally regarded as safe at the levels used for pH adjustment in oral formulations. In pediatric and elderly patients, safety concerns are mainly related to its acidic nature rather than systemic toxicity. These may include GI effects and, with repeated exposure to acidic syrups, a potential effect on dental enamel (Sheskey et al. 2017). With regard to sodium hydroxide, no evidence of toxicity was identified in the literature or in the STEP database. It is not considered to be an excipient of interest (EOI), and no acceptable daily intake (ADI) has been set (Sheskey et al. 2017; Bobillot et al. 2024).

Finally, disodium EDTA, as a chelating agent, was used in a notable number of the analyzed formulations, while it was not present in others. It has been noted in the literature in relation to reducing metal-catalyzed degradation,

enhancing the effectiveness of preservatives, stabilizing antioxidants, and improving product stability (Fox 2014). It is used in oral syrup formulations, including pediatric syrups, within acceptable limits. It is generally considered safe for pediatric populations when used at very low concentrations in syrups. High doses may be associated with hypersensitivity-related reactions and mineral chelation considerations, particularly in infants and neonates (U.S. Food and Drug Administration 2017).

The present study highlights important aspects related to the selection and disclosure of excipients in oral H₁ antihistamine formulations. Particular concerns include inadequate safety disclosure, continued use of excipients with known risks, and limited formulation transparency. The EMA and the European Commission have established frameworks that recommend safety evaluations and the disclosure of excipients with recognized effects, particularly for vulnerable populations, such as pediatric populations. The FDA also provides guidance through the Inactive Ingredient Database, which serves as a benchmark for excipient acceptability. Despite these regulatory efforts, implementation remains inconsistent, especially in countries with limited regulatory oversight in settings such as Iraq. Although the study is geographically limited, including products from multiple international manufacturers increases its relevance to other markets with similar regulatory and sourcing conditions. A key limitation of this study is that it relies solely on excipient information disclosed in PILs, which may be incomplete or outdated.

The absence of quantitative excipient concentration data precludes quantitative safety assessments. Nevertheless, within these methodological constraints, this study provides a systematic descriptive overview of excipient usage patterns in oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, with findings relevant within the analyzed formulations. This may indicate differences between regulatory expectations and formulation practices within this sample. In addition, the functional classification of excipients was primarily based on typical excipient roles reported in the literature and standard references, which may not fully reflect their true function in the final formulation.

Conclusion

This study provides an overview of the types, frequency, and combination patterns of excipients used in oral H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations. Propylene glycol, sorbitol, sodium benzoate, strawberry flavor, Sunset Yellow FCF, citric acid/sodium citrate buffer, and disodium EDTA were among the most commonly identified excipients in the analyzed formulations. The majority of the analyzed formulations contained co-solvents, and most formulations used a combination of sweeteners. All formulations in this sample contained antimicrobial preservatives, either alone or in combination. Sodium benzoate was the most frequently used antimicrobial preservative in second-generation H₁ antihistamine syrup formulations, whereas methyl and propyl parabens were more frequently used in first-generation formulations.

Colorants were not widely used. Some formulations did not contain flavoring, buffering, or chelating agents. The findings may provide descriptive insight into excipient selection patterns and formulation considerations, particularly for pediatric oral H₁ antihistamine formulations. The study also highlights the importance of excipient disclosure in PILs. Although statistically significant associations were observed between antihistamine class and excipient categories (sweeteners and preservatives), these associations may be related to manufacturer formulation strategies rather than pharmacological class-driven differences. This study provides a basis for further research on formulation practices.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The author declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

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The author declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text

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